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Research Article

DETERMINATION OF OCCURRENCE OF ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY IN PATIENTS OF TETANUS ADMITTED IN PEDIATRIC ICU

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Abstract:

Objective: Tetanus is possibly a lethal complication but still is a preventable issue. Severity of the problem, cardio-vascular issue, pulmonary & kidney complications lead to the mortality. Acute Kidney Injury is very common & fatal complication due to tetanus. This research work aimed is to find out the rate of occurrence of acute kidney injury in the patients of tetanus administered in a tertiary hospital.

Methodology: All the children from one to twelve year of age who got admission in the Pediatric ICU with diagnosis of the tetanus for a period of three years were the part of this research work. We applied PRIFLE (Pediatric risk, injury, failure, loss, end) standard to all the patients of the tetanus to classify them as having the acute kidney diseases or not, on the basis of the ECCL (Estimated Creatinine Clearance). We performed a comparison between the patients of Acute Kidney Injury & Non-Acute Kidney Injury as well as between the survivors of Acute Kidney Injury & non-Acute Kidney Injury survivors. This research work carried out at Pediatric ICU of Allied / DHQ Hospital Faisalabad for the patients suffering from tetanus who go admission March 2016 to June 2019.

Results: In the duration of this research work, the enrollment of forty-four tetanus patients carried out. About 32.0% of patients of tetanus developed acute kidney dysfunction in accordance with the standard of PRIFLE. There were total 34.09% (n: 15) deaths among the patients of tetanus in which 9 (60.0%) were present with acute renal injury. Oliguria was in observation in 35.71% (n: 5) patients. All non-survivors of Acute Kidney Injury were present with estimated creatinine clearance less than 50.0% & all patients had the autonomic not stability. Acute renal injury developed in three patients at the end of 1st week, in 4 patients in the mid of 2nd week and in 7 patients in the 3rd week. RRT (Renal Replacement Therapy) like PD (Peritoneal Dialysis) carried out in 4 patients of acute renal injury but this treatment was not able to provide improvement. The value of CRP was greater than fifty in 54.54% (n: 24) patients. We gave the support of ventilator to 85.70 % patients of acute renal injury in comparison with the 66.65 % patients from the non-Acute Kidney Injury group.

Conclusion: There are many factors for the development acute renal injury in the patients of tetanus. Most important reasons are tetanus severity, availability of the autonomic non-stability, the dependency on the ventilator & sepsis. The availability of the Acute Kidney Injury has the ability to deteriorate the tetanus outcome regarding rate of survival, duration of stay, health expenses & duration on ventilator.

keywords: Acute Kidney Injury, tetanus, methodology, RRT, PD, comparison, acute, deteriorate.

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INTRODUCTION:

Tetanus is preventable but a fatal complication and it is very serious health issue in the developing nations of various countries. There is very threatening burden of this disease on our country Pakistan. Acute Kidney Injury Tetanus is the outcome of the clostridium tetani, which has the ability to create a strong neuro-toxin, tetanospasmin influencing the CNS (Central Nervous System). It causes the development of the spasms of body, locked jaw & dysphagia in the patients. A large swing in the BP and heart beat rate are frequent secondary to the autonomic non-stability because of dis-inhibited autonomous discharge. The medical recovery follows the development of recent nerve terminals elaborating the typical prolonged illness course. The aim of the treatment is to neutralize the toxin, control of the spasm of muscle, stabilize the autonomic non-stability, wound management & monitoring of the functioning of the important organs.

Multiple drugs are in use to achieve these outcomes. There are many factors involved in the high rate of the mortality because of tetanus. Acute Kidney Injury is very lethal and common complication of tetanus. A current research work on 236 patients of intensive care unit showed a strong association between mortality due to tetanus & acute kidney injury.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was a retroactive research work. All the children from 1 month to 12 year of age who got

admission in the pediatric ICU due to tetanus were the part of this research work. The collection and recording of the medical data carried out for illness course, Acute Kidney Injury development, total stay & outcome of the patients. We performed all the necessary testing for tetanus in all the patients. We performed the biochemistry of the blood, function of kidney and analysis of urine in all the available patients. All the children suffering from tetanus as well as known kidney diseases were not the part of this research work. We excluded one patients due to abnormal renal function after scan from ultrasound. We applied the criteria of PRIFLE to all the patients of tetanus to classify them with Acute Kidney Injury or without Acute Kidney Injury, based on ECCL. The calculation of this value carried out on daily basis and we carried out adjustment of the dose depending upon the condition.

SPSS V.16 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We described the descriptive statistics with percentages. We carried out the comparison among both groups. P value of less than .050 was the significant one.

RESULTS:

In the duration of this research work, we enrolled the forty-four patients suffering from tetanus and descriptive traits of the patients are available in Table-1.

Table-I: Descriptive Characteristics Of Tetanus Patients (Total No. = 44).

Characteristic		No	Percent
Gender	Male	24.0	54.540
	Female	20.0	45.450
Age	< than 5 year	22.0	50.000
	6 - 9 year	14.0	31.810
	> 10 year	8.0	18.180
Severity	Grade I	0.0	0.000
	Grade II	7.0	15.900
	Grade III	27.0	61.360
	Grade IV	10.0	22.720
Acute Kidney Injury	Yes	14.0	31.810
	No	30.0	68.180
Outcome	Discharge	29.0	65.900
	Expiry	15.0	34.090
Instability		37.0	84.090
Ventilator		32.0	72.720
CRP	< 50	20.0	45.450
	> 50	24.0	54.540
TLC	<5,000/mm ³	5.0	11.360

	>20,000/mm ³	39.0	88.630
Hospital Stay	20 days	30.0	68.180
	25 days	14.0	31.810

Total 31.81% (n: 14) patients were present with the development of the renal dysfunction in accordance with the standard of PRIFLE. Total 34.09% (n: 15) expiries occurred among total patients of tetanus among them nine patients were present with the Acute Kidney Injury (Table-2). In the patients of Acute

Kidney Injury, no patient was in the Grade-1 or Grade-2 of severity of tetanus as all patients were in severe condition. We observed the oliguria in 35.71% (n: 5) patients. The analysis of urine was not significant in most of the cases.

Table-II: Characteristics Of Tetanus Patients With & Without Acute Kidney Injury (44).

Characteristic	Acute Kidney Injury +ve (14)		Acute Kidney Injury -ve (30)		P- Value
	No	Percent	No	Percent	
Expiries	9.0	64.280	6.0	20.000	0.0040
Blood Culture Positivity	6.0	66.660	9.0	30.000	0.0010
TLC >20,000/mm ³	11.0	78.570	6.0	20.000	0.0010
CRP >50	10.0	71.420	14.0	46.660	0.5600
Ventilator requirement	12.0	85.710	20.0	66.660	0.1880
Severity of tetanus: Grade III	10.0	71.420	17.0	56.660	0.5200
Severity of tetanus: Grade IV	4.0	28.570	6.0	20.000	
Average length of stay (days)	25.0	-	20.0	-	-

The development of the acute kidney injury carried out at the end of the 1st week in 3 patients, in the middle of 2nd week in 4 patients and in the 3rd week in 7 patients. Since the categorization of the acute kidney injury carried out in accordance with the standard of PRIFLE, 4 patients were present with ECCL from

75.0% to 50.0% & ten patients were present with ECCL less than 50.0% (Table-2). All the non-survivors of Acute Kidney Injury were present with ECCL of less than 50.0% (Table-3). The comparison of survivors & non-survivors Acute Kidney Injury are present in Table-3.

Table-III: Acute Kidney Injury Survivors Vs Acute Kidney Injury Non-Survivors (Total Acute Kidney Injury Victims = 14).

Characteristics		Survivors	Non -Survivors	P. Value
Number		5.0	9.0	0.0040
Severity Grade	Grade III	5.0	5.0	0.0010
	Grade IV	0.0	4.0	
Ventilator requirement		3.0	9.0	0.1350
TLC	>20,000/mm ³	3.0	8.0	0.0120
Blood Culture	Positive	1.0	5.0	0.0010
CRP	> 100	1.0	6.0	0.0980
Creatinine	75 - 50	4.0	0.0	0.2060
	< 50	1.0	9.0	

DISCUSSION:

The rate of mortality due to tetanus is very high with arrange from 20.0% to 50.0%. There is need of long treatment with many medicines to control the spasm. The patients can develop many related abnormalities which can alter the treatment course and illness outcomes. Renal complications are also the outcome of tetanus. Research works have displayed that up to 50.0% patients suffering from tetanus have GFR (Glomerular Filtration Rate) less than 50.0 ml/min in 1st & 2nd week of the stay in hospital. The rate of Acute Kidney Injury in the patients of tetanus ranges from 14.0% to 39.0% in various regions. In this research work, the frequency of Acute Kidney Injury was 31.81%. Creatinine of serum is not a standard marker because it does not rise, until there is decrease in the GFR as there is already loss of the function of kidney by 25.0% to 50.0%. There is influence of the mass of muscle, hydration condition, gender, and age & measurement method on the values of serum creatinine.

There is tendency for the search of the early markers of acute kidney injury. Autonomic non-stability proposed to be the major factor for Acute Kidney Injury development in both children & adults. We saw it in all the patients of this research work. Not controllable spasms of muscle resulting rhabdomyolysis & myoglobinuria causing Acute Kidney Injury is also important factor for the patients suffering from tetanus. This is not a common reason in the children of less than ten year of age.

The regular checks for the creatinine clearance and adjustment of the medicines is much necessary. The dependency on ventilator is also important factor for adverse outcome of the patients with Acute Kidney Injury. Among fourteen patients of Acute Kidney Injury, ECCL was 50.0% to 75.0% in 4 patients and they were in survivors. While ten patients were present with ECCL of less than 50.0% as Grade-3 in accordance to Acute Kidney Injury and nine patients were not survivors, showing that the Acute Kidney Injury outcome depends upon the severity. One of the main contributor of Acute Kidney Injury is Sepsis in this research with CRP as greater than one hundred in 7 patients of Acute Kidney Injury, 6 patients among them were non-survivors.

CONCLUSION:

There are many factors behind the Acute Kidney Injury development among the patients of tetanus. He most important factors are extremity of tetanus, availability of the autonomic non-stability,

dependency on the ventilator & sepsis. The Acute Kidney Injury presence can worsen the conclusion of the tetanus regarding rate of survival, duration of the patient's stay, expenses of the health care & total days on ventilation.

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